

ALL ABOUT
RESPECT

Project Report

Interim Report
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RESPECT**

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Background

The World Health Organisation estimates that 'globally about 1 in 3 (30%) of women worldwide have been subjected to either physical and/or sexual intimate partner violence or non-partner sexual violence in their lifetime' (WHO, 2024). In the UK, Deputy Chief Constable Maggie Blythe described violence against women and girls (VAWG) as a 'national emergency' (College of Police 2024), where VAWG accounted for 20% of all police recorded crime in 2022/23 (The College of Police and National Police Chiefs Council).

VAWG affects young women and girls, manifesting itself in multiple ways, examples of which include rape and sexual assault, sexual harassment, both in person and online, 'upskirting' and sexting. Ofsted (2021) reported that in one of the schools they visited, some girls reported that they could be 'contacted by up to 10 or 11 different boys a night,' asking 'for nude/semi-nude images'. Many of the young people interviewed saw this as 'part of life,' with nearly half the boys spoken to saying that they had received sexual images or videos they did not want to see either 'a lot' or 'sometimes'.

Strategies that educate young people on VAWG are, therefore, desperately needed. As UN Women suggested various methods that could be used, including the empowerment of young people to talk about the issues, and challenge rape culture. Such interventions are needed to *"shape the way they [the next generation] think about gender, respect, and human rights. Start conversations about gender roles early on, and challenge the traditional features and characteristics assigned to men and women"*.

The All About Respect project creates a space for open and honest dialogue about healthy relationships in young adults. The project brings together individuals and organisations committed to tackling Gender-Based Violence and Hate Crime in York and North Yorkshire. Working collaboratively with young adults (aged 16-25), we aim to design campaigns and training that are evidence-based and youth-led.

What we've done

In the 2023/24 and 2024/25 academic years, we have worked with young people aged 16 to 25 in education across the City of York to raise awareness of gender-based violence and hate crime and raise awareness of how to tackle this behaviour. Working with young people, we have worked in a collaborative and creative manner to seek their understanding and opinions on: 1) what is gender-based violence and hate crime, and 2) what young people think we can do to tackle this behaviour. This has included:

1. **Campaign Stalls** tied in with national and international campaign weeks (e.g., 16 Days of Activism and National Stalking Awareness Week), including activities to involve young people.
2. **Social Media campaigns** to disseminate key points and findings as part of our campaign activities.
3. **Focus Groups and Surveys** to gather data on young peoples' opinions and experiences.
4. **An Artivism competition** inviting young people to create art representing healthy and unhealthy relationships.
5. We have also delivered **bystander intervention training** to highlight how young people can challenge this behaviour.

This report

This report presents the interim findings of our work so far, highlighting the activities we have undertaken to date and some of the data provided by young people.

Activities, data collection, and data analysis are ongoing until the end of the 2024/5 academic year, when the final report will be available.

Awareness Raising

A major part of the All About Respect Project is to run campaigns and activities to raise awareness of:

1. Defining and understanding gender-based violence and hate crime.
2. How to report experiences and get help.
3. Share ideas on how we can tackle gender-based violence and hate crime.
4. Understanding the power of being a bystander.

The following pages of this report summarise some of these events and highlight key findings from our discussions and activities with young people at these events.

REACH

To date, we have:

- Held 18 events during 16 days of activism, anti-bullying week, hate crime week, Sexual Violence and Awareness week, alongside ad hoc events.
- Engaged with 988 young people through our campaign dates.
- Engaged with 4604 people through our social media and webpage.

Awareness Raising

BOLSHEE DANCEFLOOR

We have held nine events with the Bolshee Dancefloor. The aim of the event is to engage young people with the interactive dancefloor to enable a conversation about being safe on nights out.

We had much greater engagement with the dancefloor when the events were held in the community. When the dancefloor was held in educational settings during the day, young people were a little more reluctant to get involved.

Therefore, our future events are planned for more social, community events, including the Make Space for Girls events in June 2025.

The Bolshee Dancefloor

The Bolshee dancefloor are innovative pop-up dancefloor events which are organised to find out what would make people feel safer and to gather examples of unwanted behaviour.

Participants at the specially curated club can dance, chat and enjoy themselves and, if they want to, write on the Perspex dancefloor walls to share their ideas on how people should be treated in public spaces.

Awareness Raising

FEELING SAFE

As part of our campaign stalls, we conducted a 'where do you feel safe' activity where young people were asked to place a red sticker where they feel *unsafe* in York and a green sticker where they feel *safe*.

As Figure 1 shows, common areas of feeling unsafe include the river, around the snicket areas off Grape Lane and Petergate, around McDonald's, and by the bus station.

Figure 1: Feeling Safe Activity

Figure 2: Reports of why young people feel unsafe

WHY DO YOUNG PEOPLE NOT FEEL SAFE?

Young people could share their thoughts on why they feel unsafe in York, and the common themes are shown in Figure 2. As this figure shows, common themes included: 1) particular vulnerable spaces such as by the river, 2) poor lighting and concerns about darkness, 3) fears related to public transport in particular buses and trains, 4) the impact of alcohol, and 5) those in roles related to security not tackling particular issues such as doormen.

Awareness Raising

WHAT CAN WE DO TO TACKLE GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE AND HATE CRIME

As part of our campaign stalls, we run an activity where young people can share their thoughts on how we can tackle gender-based violence and hate crime in our community. Young people are invited to write on our Doodle Boards and share their thoughts and ideas.

Figure 3 shows a summary of the analysis of these comments. The comments clustered around four categories: 1) taking personal responsibility, 2) a need for greater collective social responsibility to tackle these issues, 3) more early education to foster respectful interactions and 4) more preventative solutions across our community.

Figure 3: Reports of what young people think we can do to tackle gender based violence and hate crime.

Keep your hands to yourself!

Educate men.

Respect goes both ways ♀❤♂

Awareness Raising

INAPPROPRIATE BEHAVIOUR IN A RELATIONSHIP

As part of our campaign days, we held an activity where young people could share their thoughts on the nature of unacceptable behaviours in a relationship. Young peoples' comments were analysed and are shown in Figure 4.

Young peoples' thoughts clustered around four themes: controlling behaviour, disrespectful behaviour, abusive language and manipulation.

Figure 4: Young peoples' reports of what constitutes inappropriate behaviours in a relationship.

Survey

As part of the project, we are conducting a survey with young people on their understanding and experiences of gender-based violence and hate crime. The survey is still running, but in this interim report, we report on some of the participants' (N=189) responses to date.

The first section of the survey captures young peoples understandings of gender based violence and hate crime, alongside whether they had received any information on these topics.

As shown in Figure 5, almost a third of young people had received information on the definition of gender-based violence, and a quarter had received information on hate crime.

Few young people, however, were aware of some citywide campaigns, such as Operation Vigilant, All About Respect, and the Bolshee dancefloor.

Figure 5: Awareness of GBV and Hate Crime

MORE INFORMATION

The survey is still being conducted. To find out more and to share our survey link, please visit our project website by scanning the QR code opposite or visiting:

<https://allaboutrespectysj.wordpress.com/all-about-respect-survey-2024/>

Survey

The survey also examined young peoples' experiences of gender-based violence and hate crime. Figure 6 shows the proportion of participants who reported experiencing sexual harassment, partner violence, sexual assault, and hate crime since September 2023. As this figure shows, over half the sample reported experiencing sexual harassment, a quarter of participants reported experiencing hate crime, and a roughly equal proportion of participants reported experiencing partner violence and sexual assault.

Figure 6: The prevalence of experiencing gender-based violence and hate crime

Why did participants not report their experiences?

Participants were also asked whether they had told anyone about their experiences, and if not, why. The overriding response for not reporting their experiences was participants '**playing down**' (Didn't affect me too much) or '**normalising**' (it happens to a lot of people and there are more serious matters, it's become so normalised that it's not seen as something to tell people cos it's just everyday experience) the harassment.

However, in this narrative, there were issues of **not being believed or taken seriously** (this was particularly evident in the young 16/18 group), that 'it was not worth reporting' or 'more trouble than it's worth'.

Shame, embarrassment, and a general **lack of knowledge about where to go or who to speak to** also factored into not telling others about the harassment.

FOCUS GROUPS

Alongside our survey, we are also conducting focus groups with young people to examine 1) how they understand and talk about gender-based violence, relationship violence, and hate crime, and 2) what we can do to tackle these behaviours in our community. The initial analysis has identified the themes summarised below.

Young people discussed **a range of behaviours** when discussing gender based violence and hate crime, including street harassment, assault and problematic behaviours in relationships. Young people also highlighted terms not commonly used, such as *hoovering* (“being forced/ sucked back into a destructive relationship”).

Participants raised **concerns about the Incel culture** online. Young people also reported feeling a lot of fear when faced with this culture online and a sense of powerlessness on how to challenge this.

Normalisation: Lots of the young people highlighted that gender-based violence and hate crime were so normalised and an expected part of life. This was particularly the case online, where young people talked about the prevalence of inappropriate image sharing.

Not knowing how to report experiences was flagged as an issue young people face when reporting gender based violence and hate crime. This became a barrier to reporting as it was not perceived as easy to do.

Age-appropriate education was highlighted as a real need at an ever-younger age. Participants highlighted that they don't want just to be talked at, but the need for engaging activities to teach about these challenging behaviours.

Our focus groups are continuing to the end of the 2024/5 academic year. If you would like us to conduct a focus group with young people you work with, please get in touch.

Prevention

BYSTANDER INTERVENTION TRAINING

The All About Respect Bystander Training course aims to empower young people to become active bystanders and help prevent sexual harassment, sexual harm, and hate crime. The training equips young people with the skills and awareness needed to notice warning signs and techniques that enable them to intervene while staying safe. Our training includes information on:

- What Do We Mean By 'Bystander'?
- What Is Gender-Based Violence, including sexual harassment, sexual assault and partner violence?
- What Is Hate Crime?
- How Do We Intervene?

We tried several ways to deliver the training in person to young people, but faced several challenges:

- Students not signing up for the training
- difficulties in finding times in students' timetables to fit in the two-hour training session
- a reluctance from students to sign up for the two-hour training.

In consultation with young people, we amended the training and recorded this as four 15-minute videos that could be watched at a time convenient to the students. There is a quiz to complete, and if completed, students will receive a certificate of completion.

OUR BYSTANDER INTERVENTION TRAINING

You can find out more about our bystander intervention training by visiting:

<https://allaboutrespectysj.wordpress.com/bystander-intervention-training/>

Or scanning the QR code below

MORE INFORMATION

Prevention

Operation Vigilant

We have been evaluating the effectiveness of Operation Vigilant. A North Yorkshire police initiative, originally developed in Thames Valley, uses a community policing approach to prevent sexual harassment before it occurs. In doing so, it also aims to build positive relations with the community, including by increasing feelings of safety. Through a community-based survey, we asked participants about the following:

- Perceptions of York (e.g., safety)
- Experiences on nights out in York (e.g., experiencing hate crime)
- Attitudes towards the police (e.g., fairness)

A total of 361 people took part, with a mean age of 37.48 (SD = 12.81), with 62% of those identifying as female. The key findings of the survey are presented below.

Safety

78.1% of those surveyed felt that York was safer/much safer than other cities. Females and non-binary participants felt significantly less safe during nights out than did males. This may explain why females had significantly fewer nights out in York; on average, they went out less than once a month.

Few participants had heard of York-based initiatives that tackle sexual violence and hate crime, which suggests more needs to be done to publicise these initiatives. Those who had been victimised were significantly more aware of initiatives, which may explain why they did not differ in terms of feelings of safety nor attitudes towards the police (note – victimisation is correlated with more negative attitudes).

Prevention

Operation Vigilant

Experiences

When asked about experiences on nights out in York in the last four months, there were fairly high rates of experiencing aggression on nights out (defined as victimisation and/or witnessing aggression). Figure 7 below provides a breakdown of the type of victimisation experienced by type of event; notably, GBV was the most common reported.

Figure 7: The prevalence of negative experiences on night out

Attitudes Towards the Police

Females were more willing to cooperate with the police but had less positive attitudes overall, as did those identifying as neurodivergent.

Operation Vigilant Final Report

The final report on the Operation Vigilant survey will provide a further breakdown of the data, analysing the questions by key demographics including gender, age and disability.

The final report will be available on our project website.

Summary

Activities for the All About Respect project will continue up to the end of the 2024/25 academic year.

Our activities conducted so far have highlighted:

- Where young people feel safe and why they feel unsafe, including poor lighting and the impact of alcohol.
- Their thoughts on how we can tackle gender-based violence in our community, including the need for more education.
- The lack of awareness of some initiatives designed to tackle gender-based violence and hate crime.
- How they understand partner violence and what behaviours they define as unacceptable in relationships.
- Their experiences of gender based violence and hate crime, alongside other experiences on nights out.

Our activities are continuing and will include:

- Events focused on 1) hate speech and misogynistic language use in York schools and colleges, 2) stalking and unhealthy relationships, and 3) bystander behaviours.
- Our final report will be available in Summer 2025.

If you would like us to run our events and activities with the young people you work with or if you have any questions about our work please do get in touch.

Acknowledgements

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- The York and North Yorkshire Policing, Fire, Crime and Commissioning
- The Public Health team at the City of York Council
- The Impact Assessment Activity fund at the University of York

We would also like to thank all the schools, colleges and universities who have supported our activities.

A special thank you for all the young people who have got involved in the project and shared their thoughts on how we can tackle gender-based violence and hate crime in York.

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**ALL ABOUT
RESPECT**